

Gearing Up Towards Organizational Agility? First, Let Go of the AutoPilot

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Introduction: Aspiring to Organizational Agility

In the ever-evolving, complex landscape of modern business, Organizational Agility (OA) stands as a beacon of strategic capability, enabling organizations to not just survive but to thrive. Anna-Theresa Walter describes OA as a “learned, permanently-available dynamic capability,” a paradoxical blend of stability and adaptability, underscoring its critical role in helping companies flourish in rapidly changing environments [Walter21]. This portrayal of OA as both a consistent asset and a flexible skill highlights the complex nature of agility in today’s volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous [VUCA02] world.

Despite its recognized importance, as evidenced by McKinsey [McKinsey22] and Gallup [Gallup22], achieving true OA is a formidable challenge. Agile transformations have propelled advancements in specific sectors like IT project delivery, yet many organizations grapple with expanding these practices into a comprehensive, organizational-wide agility. This difficulty accentuates the necessity for an approach that transcends methodological changes to permeate deeply into the organization’s ethos [ScrumAlliance18].

A significant hurdle in this journey is the tendency of agile transformations to operate on autopilot. Organizations often select a framework and practices akin to a roadmap and adhere to them without challenging their existing mental models. This approach, while providing structure, often leads to superficial agility. The popular SAFe agile framework [SAFe21], for example, recommends Kotter’s “dual operating system” approach [Kotter14], where traditional structures are retained while an agile layer is superimposed. The ensuing results are more frequent deliveries but a lack of fostering innovation or fully engaging the workforce.

The path to genuine Organizational Agility (OA) is often obstructed by a mechanistic view of organizations, a fact further reinforced by Morgan's critique. [Morgan06]. This perspective paradoxically leads to agile roles, initially intended as flexible scaffoldings, being transformed into static titles in many organizations. This misinterpretation is a direct consequence of the mechanistic worldview's demand for rigid structures, overshadowing the intended flexibility and adaptability of agile roles.

Such a rigid interpretation of agility erodes trust and impedes talent retention, a concern echoed by McGregor & Doshi [McGregorDoshi17] and further explored in studies by MIT Sloan [MITSloan21] and the World Economic Forum [WEF21]. However, advancements in organizational science offer hope, highlighting the significance of contextuality in coordination [Mintzberg23] and recognizing OA as a set of dynamic capabilities essential for resilience and adaptability [Panizzon20].

In practice, agility often devolves into a rote and blind implementation of practices, losing sight of their original intent and context. To counter this, a shift away from an "agile on autopilot" approach towards embodying a "fluid agile" model is necessary — a model that adapts organizational structures and processes to the specific context at hand.

This article aims to demystify OA by integrating the resilience of the natural world with the structured adaptability of the Agile Gearbox concept. We propose a theoretical framework that balances the paradox of OA's permanent yet dynamic nature, offering a nuanced understanding of agility. Our goal is to guide organizations beyond the limitations of traditional agile transformations, gearing up towards a future where agility is an actively nurtured, intrinsic part of navigating the VUCA environments.

1. Agile Agility: Beyond Traditional Methods

Organizational Agility (OA) is more than the sum of agile methods; it's about the inherent adaptability of an organization's structure and capabilities. Inspired by Henry Mintzberg's research, we see agility as the ability to reshape organizational forms in response to environmental changes [Mintzberg23]. This adaptability, as conceptualized by David J. Teece in his seminal work on Dynamic Capabilities [Teece97], is vital but only part of the story.

Delving deeper, we find that Dynamic Capabilities (DC) and New Product Development Ability (NPDA) offer further insights. Like a cheetah adapting its strategy for each prey, organizations must innovate for each market shift. However, the effectiveness of these adaptations can vary; as research on Reorganization Dynamic Capabilities suggests, the success of structural changes is context-dependent.

This leads to a key realization: agility requires a nuanced approach, one that respects the diverse and shifting contexts within different parts of an organization. This understanding paves the way for a superculture — a foundational cultural shift that underpins and enables the entire ecosystem of organizational agility.

Contextual Coordination: Embracing Multi-Form Agility

In our inquiry into Organizational Agility (OA), we confront a pivotal question: How do some organizations adeptly

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adapt to their environment, embodying agility in its truest form? This quest leads us to the intersection of agility and contextuality in organizational structures, where Henry Mintzberg's research offers enlightening perspectives.

We find a useful analytical framework based on Henry Mintzberg's seminal work on organizational structures, which he refined over four decades of new insights [Mintzberg23]. Mintzberg's framework, as it is now situated, delineates four main distinct organizational forms, each suited to specific contexts. Yet, their agility is not without boundaries:

- **Personal Enterprise:** Thrives in volatile, centralized environments. A visionary leader guides directly, making quick adjustments but hitting scalability limits. Typified by visionary leaders like Steve Jobs, these organizations navigate dynamic, centralized environments with agility. However, does this form falter when faced with the demands of scalability and broader, decentralized decision-making?
- **Project Pioneer:** Operates in fluid, decentralized settings. Teams coordinate through information sharing and mutual adjustments. Reflective of IDEO's innovative ethos, these structures thrive in fluid, decentralized contexts. Yet, one wonders, is this form still suited and the most efficient in a stable environment?
- **Professional Assembly:** Suited for stable, decentralized landscapes. Expertise is the linchpin of coordination, allowing professionals to function autonomously. Exemplified by institutions like universities or hospitals, where specialized expertise (proficiency) governs coordination in stable, decentralized settings. The inquiry is about their ability to remain agile under rapid changes that demand quick, cross-functional coordination.
- **Programmed Machine:** Ideal for stable, centralized setups, focusing on standardized work and streamlined operations for predictable outcomes. Organizations like McDonald's demonstrate efficient operations in stable, centralized environments. This poses a question: are there instances where such programmed structures struggle to adapt swiftly to unforeseen market dynamics?

Four main forms of organizations [Mintzberg23]

Notably, these forms aren't mutually exclusive nor confined to entire organizations. Organizations can be hybrids, incorporating different forms within various departments or units. The key to enduring agility and resilience lies in an organization's ability to morph these forms in response to shifting contexts and objectives. In other words, agility is not just an organization-wide phenomenon; individual parts of the organization must also have the flexibility to adapt and reorganize according to their unique contextual demands. However, this level of organizational adaptation often encounters internal coordination and control challenges, which have been ingrained through a company's historical and cultural development. For example, standardized workflows, like those introduced by new accountancy rules, can inadvertently embed bureaucracies within organizational hierarchies. This is ironic, considering Max Weber's concept of Bureaucracy [Weber22] was initially intended to increase efficiency. Yet, in contexts where stability is lacking and changes are frequent, Weber's model may lead to stagnation. Consequently, organizations often shift towards solution-oriented approaches, with traditional agile methods frequently serving as their initial response.

This natural inclination towards traditional agile methods is often a comfortable fit within the Project Pioneer form, which offers a familiar framework for managing change. However, true agility involves not only evolving and merging these forms as circumstances dictate but also developing the capacity to support such evolution.

For instance, an organization may initially operate as a Personal Enterprise but may later identify more stable elements, typically at the interfaces between teams, and evolve toward a Professional Assembly for optimized scaling. Indeed, this transition is often recommended by Agile scaling models, which advocate following a team-of-teams approach (e.g., SAFe's train, Scrum of Scrums, etc.). However, it's important to note that even these interfaces evolve over time, and agile frameworks often lack guidance on monitoring this stability and reorganizing accordingly.

Henry Mintzberg's analysis of Organizational Forms uncovers a crucial insight: each form is uniquely suited to specific contexts, with its own set of advantages and limitations. However, as organizational contexts evolve, so must our approach to agility. This means embracing a multifaceted, hybrid configuration, where organizations dynamically reconfigure themselves to match changing environments, rather than adhering to a single, rigid form.

While adaptable organizational forms provide the structural foundation for agility, realizing agility also requires developing certain dynamic skills and competencies within companies. Organizational forms represent potential vessels; dynamic capabilities describe the functional traits that bring these structures to life. As we explore in the next section, empirical research has uncovered distinct capabilities that drive organizations' agility and resilience.

Dynamic Capabilities: Proven Characteristics of Organizational Agility

The journey to understand Organizational Agility (OA) leads us into the realm of Dynamic Capabilities (DC), a concept critical for adapting to environmental changes. This understanding, as expounded in the work of Mateus Panizzon and others, provides a framework for exploring why some companies excel in adapting to environmental shifts, grounding our inquiry into the realm of Knowledge-Based Dynamic Capabilities [Panizzon20].

The NPDA Theory: A New Understanding of Agility

The concept of New Product Development Ability (NPDA) stands at the forefront of Organizational Agility (OA), providing a specialized perspective on how organizations adapt and innovate. Mateus Panizzon's research offers a groundbreaking view of NPDA, demonstrating that it is not just about the ability to develop new products but also a broader reflection of an organization's agility.

NPDA is akin to an agile predator, each new product representing a new "prey" in a continually shifting environment. Panizzon has shown that NPDA stems from a synergistic blend of critical capabilities, each playing a pivotal role in an organization's agile response to market changes. These include:

- **Reconfiguration Capability:** This is the cornerstone of agility, reflecting a company's ability to reorient and realign its resources in response to new challenges. It involves how a company can swiftly initiate, develop, and launch new products, outpacing competitors by effectively reassembling resources, whether they be teams, budgets, or priorities.
- **Technological Capability:** Integral to reconfiguration, this capability involves the adoption and integration of advanced technologies, such as AI and 3D manufacturing, to enhance product development processes. It highlights how technology can break silos and speed up information flow, which is crucial for agility in

today's digital landscape.

- **International Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO):** This capability measures a company's proactive, risk-managing, and innovation-oriented culture, especially in international markets. It directly impacts technological capability, fostering a mindset open to new technologies and innovative approaches.
- **Organizational Creativity:** A key driver of NPDA, this capability focuses on creating an environment conducive to generating new and useful ideas. It's about fostering a culture where innovation is not just encouraged but is a fundamental part of the organization's DNA.
- **Learning Capability:** This encompasses collective learning and knowledge creation, essential for innovation and development of new products. It relates to how organizations learn from experiences, feedback, and how they create new knowledge, particularly in the context of product innovation.

Together, these capabilities, measurable through Structural Equation Modeling, account for about 80% of NPDA's variance or explainability. This theory highlights the predictors of NPDA and establishes it as a form of Organizational Agility grounded in knowledge-based dynamic capabilities.

Panizzon's research underscores that NPDA is a manifestation of agility particularly relevant in manufacturing industries, where the turbulence and competitiveness of international markets demand a high degree of adaptability at the market level (such as new customer requisites) and technological level (with emergent technologies). This adaptability, reflected in superior product innovation performance, is not just about individual teams adopting agile tools; it signifies a broader organizational configuration that supports a superculture conducive to agility.

This expanded understanding of NPDA, as articulated by Panizzon, reshapes our perception of agility from a narrow focus on agile tools to a broader appreciation of the cultural and structural elements integral to an organization's adaptive prowess.

How do these dynamic capabilities, as detailed in Panizzon's NPDA theory, interact with the organizational environment? Let's delve into this question, guided by Mintzberg's frameworks.

A Reorganization Dynamic Capability: Adapting to Change

Reconfiguration Capability is vital, as it reflects an organization's proficiency in reallocating resources to meet new challenges. This capability brings us to an intriguing aspect of OA: the Reorganization Dynamic Capability. In their study, Girod and others have differentiated between two forms of reorganization: the more pervasive restructuring and the more focused reconfiguration. They found that in dynamic environments, reconfiguration often leads to more positive outcomes, while in stable environments, restructuring, which involves more comprehensive changes across the organization, tends to be more effective [Girod17].

This dichotomy resonates with Mintzberg's research, suggesting that the choice between restructuring and reconfiguration should be context-dependent. For example, in a stable environment, there may be less need for the flexibility of a Project Pioneer form and more focus on efficiency as seen in a Programmed Machine form. Conversely, in dynamic environments, the agility afforded by reconfiguration aligns more with the adaptability needed.

It's important to understand that more unstable or stable environments can be related with industry life cycles. Some industries, like Information Technology (IT), have faster change rates than food processing, container manufacturing or beverage bottling, which is explained by several structural factors, such as market concentration, international regulation dependence, funds for research, costs for innovation and customers' power of choice. What five years represents in terms of the IT industry, is very different from food processing. A Reorganization Capability, therefore, denotes both restructuring and reorganizing, and is contextual. This underlines its nature as a *Dynamic Capability*.

Understanding these industry-specific dynamics paves the way for a deeper examination of the "environment" from an agile practitioner's perspective, where the focus shifts to how internal organizational segments experience stability and dynamism differently.

The Organizational Environment as a Dynamic Mosaic

In reevaluating Organizational Agility (OA), we must question the assumption of a homogeneous environment within the entire organization. Mintzberg's observation of many organizations being hybrids suggests a more complex reality, and further field observations indicate even finer granularity in how different parts of an organization experience their environment.

From the vantage point of individual workers or teams, every day involves making judgments about which aspects of their work are stable and which are dynamic, as well as what needs centralized decision-making versus decentralization. Every work system is a blend of both stable and dynamic components, and we encourage readers to identify elements of their own work that fit into each of these categories.

Adapting to this environmental variability involves a strategic allocation of effort. For example, in software development, a principle from the XP (eXtreme Programming [Beck00] agile method known as YAGNI ("You Ain't Gonna Need It") advises against adding features until they become necessary. While this approach aims to maintain simplicity, it often leaves out important assumptions, particularly about stable parts of the system or centrally made architectural decisions. Such omissions can lead to hidden costs and risks. Recognizing that the environment is more complex and variable than traditionally assumed is crucial for effectively managing these dynamic and stable elements.

The most subtle changes in an organization's environment are often best known by frontline workers, those in direct contact with customers or deeply involved in technical aspects. These workers are adept at sensing changes in their specific areas and adapting accordingly. This reality implies the need for decentralizing OA, accommodating changes in coordination at various levels of the organization, from individual departments to teams.

This reality leads us to a critical question: How can this individual and team-level "sensing and responding" be effectively scaled across the entire organization? What kind of organizational culture is necessary to support this decentralized, nuanced approach to agility?

In pondering these questions, we recognize the organizational environment not as a single entity but as a dynamic mosaic of varying elements. Understanding and embracing this complexity is key to cultivating a culture

where agility is appropriately scaled and adapted to each unique segment of the organization.

Navigating Reorganizations: The Superculture of Agility (SCA)

In the pursuit of Organizational Agility, focusing on continual adaptation and reorganization, a pivotal question emerges: Does this pursuit threaten the existing organizational cultures or even the core identities of companies? Such a transformation, characterized by the adoption of new structures and dynamic capabilities, may seem to destabilize the established norms and values that define the organization or its departments. Yet, this journey need not be one of cultural erosion. Instead, it can be a path towards evolving and enriching organizational identity through the concept of a “superculture.”

A superculture is not just a unifying framework but a dynamic interplay of fluidity and unity. It allows organizations to maintain their foundational ethos while embracing the necessary fluidity and responsiveness demanded by agility. This agility superculture transcends traditional boundaries and silos, fostering an environment where change is not only accepted but anticipated and skillfully navigated by everyone. It's about a collective movement, where each part of the organization aligns and moves together for the greater good, yet retains the flexibility to adapt as needed.

Thus, true Organizational Agility is not about rigidly adhering to one form or culture. It's about creating a cultural metamorphosis — a superculture that preserves the organization's core identity while enabling smooth adaptation to new contexts and challenges. It's in this balance — preserving core cultural essence while dynamically adapting to change — that the agility superculture thrives. As we explore what constitutes this superculture, we will uncover how it facilitates the organization's capacity to adapt to changing contexts and goals.

With our understanding of the agility superculture taking shape, let's return to the quintessential symbol of agility — the cheetah — by exploring its traits and behaviors, helps unravel how these can illuminate the key components of an effective agility culture within organizations.

2. Embodying Agility - Lessons from the Cheetah

In the quest to understand and implement Organizational Agility (OA), we can draw powerful lessons from the natural world. One of the most compelling metaphors for agility is the cheetah, renowned for its speed, adaptability, and prowess. By examining the characteristics of this magnificent animal, we can glean insights into what makes an organization truly agile. Each aspect of the cheetah's life and behavior parallels organizational practices, providing a vivid and relatable guide to embodying agility in our work environments.

Playfulness: Learning and Adapting with Agility (a)

In the wild, cheetah cubs spend about 18 months with their mother, learning the art of the hunt. This period is not just about survival skills; it's also a time for play, exploration, and learning. The cubs' playful activities are crucial for developing their hunting abilities, helping them understand their environment, and enhancing their agility.

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In organizations, “playfulness” reflects a similar spirit of exploration and learning. It’s about creating an environment where employees feel safe to experiment, try new approaches, and learn from both successes and failures. This aspect of agility requires adopting new forms of working and coordinating with others. It includes how individuals use their expertise and communicate about their work. Just like the cheetah cubs, employees need time, space, and a supportive culture to learn and use each form depending on the context.

Playfulness in an organizational setting is not about being carefree or unserious; it’s about cultivating a learning culture where curiosity and innovation are valued. It’s about encouraging teams to be agile in their thinking and approaches, constantly adapting to new challenges and opportunities. This culture fosters a dynamic work environment where continuous improvement is a collective goal, mirroring the cheetah’s adaptability and resilience.

Organizations that embrace playfulness encourage their teams to experiment with new ideas and approaches. They understand that agility is not just about existing skills but also about developing new ones that the evolving context calls for. This approach leads to a more resilient organization capable of navigating the complexities and uncertainties of the modern business landscape.

Nervous System: Enhancing Sensory Awareness for Organizational Agility (b)

The cheetah, in its natural habitat, exemplifies the essence of a sophisticated “nervous system.” Before embarking on a high-speed chase, the cheetah spends considerable time observing and stalking its prey. This process involves a heightened state of alertness, where every sense gathers information about its environment. The cheetah’s attention and focus during this phase are as crucial as its physical prowess. Notably, the cheetah is not just focused externally; it is also acutely aware of its internal state, ensuring it is optimal for the hunt.

Sensors and Curiosity: The Generation of Information (b1)

Translating this into an organizational setting, we see the parallel in developing a robust system of “sensors” — both interoceptive (internal) and exteroceptive (external). In an agile organization, these sensors represent the mechanisms and channels through which employees, at all levels, observe and gather information about their environment. It’s about fostering a culture where curiosity is encouraged, allowing employees to seek out new information, ask probing questions, and remain vigilant to both internal organizational shifts and external market changes. This curiosity-driven approach ensures that the organization, like the cheetah, is always attuned to the nuances of its surroundings, ready to respond effectively to opportunities and threats.

Transparency: Facilitating the Flow of Information (b2)

Transparency in communication and decision-making processes is akin to the cheetah’s efficient and coordinated use of its senses. It’s about ensuring that the information gathered through these organizational sensors flows freely throughout the company. This transparency is crucial for agility, as it enables swift decision-making and coordinated action. In an agile organization, information should not be hoarded but shared openly, ensuring every team member is informed and empowered to act. This open flow of information builds trust, fosters collaboration, and enhances the collective agility of the organization, much like the cheetah’s cohesive

and precise response to its environment.

Contextual Transparency (b3)

However, akin to a cheetah selectively closing its senses while resting to filter out unimportant signals, effective organizational transparency is also contextual. Not all information is equally beneficial for widespread dissemination. If shared inappropriately, some data can create unwanted noise, distract from key objectives, or compromise the organization's security. Hence, while fostering an open information culture, it's crucial to discern what information is shared and with whom. This nuanced approach to transparency respects the need for strategic discretion, balancing openness with the organization's overall safety and effectiveness. We will revisit the subtleties of this approach when discussing trust in subsection (d), exploring how calibrated transparency contributes to a secure and agile organization.

By integrating these aspects — the sensory awareness akin to the cheetah's observational skills and the transparent flow of information within the organization — we create a responsive and agile organizational nervous system. This system is key to adapting swiftly to changing contexts, ensuring that the organization, like the cheetah, is always primed for effective action.

Self-Care: The Unsung Hero of Organizational Agility (c)

The cheetah, renowned for its incredible bursts of speed, actually spends a minimal portion of its day in these high-energy activities. In fact, cheetahs typically spend only up to three minutes running at high speeds; the majority of their time is devoted to resting, sleeping, and caring for their family. This balance between exertion and rest is essential for their survival and effectiveness as hunters.

This aspect of the cheetah's life sheds light on an often-overlooked component of agility in organizations: self-care and well-being. Just like the cheetah, employees in an agile organization require periods of rest and recovery to maintain their performance and avoid burnout. Incorporating self-care into the workplace goes beyond ensuring physical well-being; it also includes mental and social health. This approach is in stark contrast to cultures that glorify overwork and undervalue rest, often referred to as "toxic" cultures. Prioritizing self-care leads to more sustainable performance and a healthier work environment.

Furthermore, self-care in an organization extends to creating a culture where employees feel comfortable discussing nuances, insights, and even half-baked ideas without fear of judgment. This requires building an environment of genuine care and support among peers, where individuals are valued not just for their output but for their overall well-being.

To foster sustainability and resilience in agile organizations, adopting practices from "Commoning" or the "Core Design Principles for Governing the Commons" can be beneficial. These principles, as outlined by Elinor Ostrom in her groundbreaking work on managing shared resources, emphasize the collective care and sustainable management of the organization's common pool of talent and resources [Ostrom90]. Just as cheetahs manage their time and energy efficiently within their family groups, organizations need to ensure fair and sustainable use of their resources, fostering a culture where people care for each other as well as for the organization's goals.

Skeleton and Skin: Dual Trust in Organizational Agility (d)

In the animal kingdom, the cheetah's agility and effectiveness in hunting are not just due to its physical prowess but also its social structures, such as coalitions formed by cheetah brothers. These coalitions combine the structural strength of kinship (akin to a skeleton) with the bonds of fraternity (comparable to skin), creating a powerful system that supports agility and extends across multiple individuals.

Breaking down silos in an organization, akin to maintaining fluidity in the cheetah's movement, requires nurturing a culture of trust. This natural analogy offers insights into a dual system of trust in organizations.

Defining Trust in Organizations

In an organizational setting, trust is fundamentally about believing that others will act in the organization's best interest. This type of trust is essential for operational efficiency, as it allows individuals to rely on their colleagues' competence and reliability, especially in situations where complete knowledge or specific skills are lacking. This trust enables collaborative work environments to function effectively, fostering a culture of dependability and shared responsibility.

Skeleton: The Structure of Generalized Trust (d1)

In organizations, the "skeleton" - encompassing bones, muscles, and ligaments - symbolizes the structure that supports strength and speed. This represents generalized trust, which is derived from rules-based systems within the organization. Just as a cheetah's skeleton provides the necessary framework for movement, generalized trust provides a stable and predictable foundation for organizational operations. It is built on established rules, roles, norms and hierarchies, facilitating swift decision-making and coordinated action.

Generalized Trust in an Organizational Context "Generalized trust" (or "cognitive trust") in this paper refers to confidence in the broader organizational system and its members, extending beyond personal relationships. It involves a belief in the collective adherence to the organization's norms and the effective fulfillment of roles by its members. This form of trust is crucial in larger or more complex organizations where direct personal relationships with all members are impractical. By trusting in the organizational structure and the general reliability of its members, generalized trust facilitates efficient collaboration and decision-making across various levels of the organization.

Skin and Tissues: Unity and Sensitivity through Affective Trust (d2)

Contrasting the structure of the skeleton is the skin and tissues, representing the unity and sensitivity provided by affective trust. In a cheetah's family, the nurturing and learning environment is akin to the sensitivity of skin and tissues, allowing for adaptability and responsiveness. "Affective trust" is about personal bonds and emotional connections, fostering a sense of unity and supporting a culture where complex nuances and ideas can be navigated effectively.

Self-Care and Affective Trust One might wonder, does emphasizing self-care and affective trust mean tolerating a lack of productivity or "laziness" in the workplace? It's important to understand that

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people are inherently not lazy. The duality of human needs involves seeking self-esteem — such as through risk-taking and achieving a sense of progress — and a desire for safety and stability. Recognizing these dual needs is crucial, as individuals who find their work meaningful and align with these needs tend to naturally engage and contribute effectively. This understanding is vital for fostering an environment that motivates and values employees. This insight underscores the importance of aligning organizational tasks with individual motivations and creating an environment where employees feel valued and part of a cohesive whole.

The Necessity of Dual Trust Systems for Agility: The ART of Trust (d3)

Adaptive Relational Trust (ART) represents the dynamic nature of trust in agile organizations. It involves developing the ability to shift between generalized and affective trust depending on the situation. Developing this ART is akin to mastering a craft and is crucial for managing information flow within organizations (b2).

The ART (Adaptive Relational Trust) of Trust: Contextual Shifts in Trust (d4)

While transparency is key to agility, not all information can or should be shared universally, as discussed in (b3). ART allows not only for flexibility but also for the nuanced handling of information. “Trusting cognitive trust” ensures that transparency does not compromise the organization’s security or create unnecessary noise. It enables teams to understand when to share information openly and when discretion is required, maintaining trust even when full transparency is not feasible.

Equity and Collaboration: Key to Organizational Agility (e)

In nature, just like there’s no hierarchy between a cheetah’s organs or limbs, each part playing an essential role, a similar dynamic is crucial in organizations. The concepts of self-care (c) and trust (d) lead to understanding the equal importance of all actors within an organization. Just as harming any part of a cheetah increases risk and reduces performance, in an agile organization, the marginalization of any member can have detrimental effects.

The focus shifts from competition between individuals to collaboration first, encouraging what could be termed “friendly competition” - competition between ideas, not people. This collaborative environment, where people care about each other’s well-being, is more conducive to innovation and problem-solving than a purely competitive one.

In contrast to the replaceable nature of parts in Programmed Machines or the centralization in Personal Enterprises, agile organizations recognize the potential for any part to take on various roles. This versatility requires a departure from traditional hierarchical structures, emphasizing the importance of every individual, irrespective of their role or title. Such an approach ensures that everyone feels valued and can contribute meaningfully, regardless of their position.

Just as affective trust is necessary across all levels of an organization, so too is a sense of equity. This may involve reassessing and possibly eliminating perceptions of unfair treatment arising from titles or pay discrepancies. By doing so, organizations can create a more cohesive and supportive environment.

With the combination of safety (c), trust (d), and equity (e), organizations embody the three essential elements for mutual aid, as highlighted by Servigne and Chapelle [ServigneChapelle17]. Humans thrive in such environments, as evidenced by Kropotkin's work [Kropotkin02]. This not only increases resilience but also reduces fragility, creating a robust and adaptable organizational culture.

Survival Instinct: The Power of Intrinsic Motivation in Organizational Agility (f)

In the animal kingdom, the survival instinct is a compelling force, particularly evident in the cheetah. This instinct, the strongest form of motivation, propels the cheetah to utilize all its energy in pursuit of survival. Remarkably, this drive is internal; no external force can compel the cheetah to exert such immense effort. This natural phenomenon serves as a profound metaphor for intrinsic motivation in organizations.

In the context of organizations and human behavior, intrinsic motivation, as described by Deci and Ryan [DeciRyan85], plays a role akin to the cheetah's survival instinct. It is a powerful internal force that drives individuals to engage in tasks with enthusiasm and dedication. This type of motivation is more potent and sustainable than external incentives, as it originates from within the individual, tapping into their deepest values and interests.

Unlike extrinsic motivators, which can be controlled and manipulated, intrinsic motivation is inherently personal and less direct to influence. It arises from an individual's desires and passions, making it a more genuine and robust energy source. When harnessed effectively, intrinsic motivation can inspire people to go above and beyond, pushing the boundaries of their capabilities.

Intrinsic motivation aligns closely with the concept of self-care and regeneration (c). When individuals are motivated by internal factors, they tend to experience higher levels of satisfaction and well-being, contributing to a regenerative work environment. Additionally, this form of motivation plays a significant role in building trust (d) within an organization. When team members are intrinsically motivated, they are more likely to be committed, reliable, and authentic in their interactions, fostering a culture of mutual trust and respect.

Versatility: The Essence of Organizational Agility (g)

The concept of versatility in Organizational Agility (OA) can be likened to the adaptive behaviors of a cheetah in the wild. Just as cheetahs rest in stable environments and leap into action when hunting opportunities arise, agile organizations must exhibit a similar level of fluency. They need the skill to re-organize parts of themselves at will, adapting seamlessly to new contexts. This organizational fluency, derived from the insights in contextual coordination (1a), is about the dynamic capability to switch between different operational modes, like the cheetah alternating between rest and pursuit.

This versatility is not just a structural attribute but a cultural one, deeply embedded in the organization's DNA. It's about creating an environment where all parts of the organization, inspired by the cheetah's "nervous system" and sense of "playfulness," are perpetually ready to reconfigure for optimal performance. Crucial to this is the engagement of all actors, from leadership to frontline employees, in cross-functional collaborations. Mary Parker Follett, a pioneering thinker in the early 20th century, championed the "power-with" approach to management

[MeleRosanas03]. Her ideas, advocating collaborative decision-making over hierarchical control, remain strikingly relevant a century later. True agility emerges from this ethos, where decision-making is shared across all levels, fostering trust and a sense of ownership. The best results are obtained when structures and norms are co-created by the members themselves, ensuring minimal yet effective rules that align with the organization's objectives.

The concept of versatility in OA highlights the need for collective engagement and shared decision-making in fostering a dynamic and adaptable organizational culture. As we reflect on these insights and their parallels with the cheetah's adaptability, it becomes important to recognize the boundaries of such animal analogies. Animals, with their fixed physical structures and innate behaviors, offer only a partial view of the dynamic, evolving nature of organizations. As we navigate the aspects of a Superculture of Agility, it becomes evident that the journey toward organizational agility is not just about adopting animalistic traits. Instead, it involves fostering an environment conducive to the conscious evolution of organizational practices and ethos.

In the upcoming section, we will delve deeper into the interplay between culture and structure. We will examine how the Agile Gearbox metaphor can be used to conceptualize and implement a structure that is both flexible and robust, facilitating the seamless transition between different modes of operation and ensuring sustained agility in the face of ever-changing business landscapes.

3. Shifting Gears in Agile Organizations: the Agile Gearbox

Organizational agility often begins on a predefined path, akin to an automatic vehicle set on a familiar route. To truly embody agility, however, organizations must learn to adapt, shifting gears with awareness and intentionality. This section delves into the mechanistic metaphor of an agile gearbox, specifically tailored to be easily grasped and utilized by everyone within the organization, creating a common language that transcends complex and nuanced worldviews.

Embracing a Shared Understanding of Agility

To prevent conflicts about the best organization for the context and enable change that is both effective and scalable, we propose a simple metaphor that everyone in the organization can rally around: the "agile gearbox". It's a concept that encourages a more conscious and mindful approach to organizational structuring. Unlike the autopilot mode of adopting one-size-fits-all agile frameworks or methods, the agile gearbox metaphor invites individuals within the organization to first assess their context thoroughly, and then select the most suitable method of coordination.

Mapping Gearbox to Organizational Forms

The agile gearbox metaphor is designed to be intuitive and easy to grasp, providing a new model and narrative for understanding and implementing agility. Each "gear" in this metaphor corresponds to a specific organizational form, allowing for a tailored approach to agility:

1. **Personal Enterprise (Gear 1)**: Sets the organization in motion, perfect for dynamic, centralized contexts,

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yet it's not designed for growth beyond a certain point.

2. **Project Pioneer (Reverse Gear):** Encourages a creative, inquisitive stance, prompting a look back to leap forward. The idea of going “reverse” is to identify the assumptions that no longer help and need changing. It is about innovation and rethinking work, but it's a temporary state, not a constant mode of operation.
3. **Professional Assembly (Gears 2 or 3):** With stability found, the organization accelerates as multiple teams coordinate around stable interfaces, working both independently and together.
4. **Programmed Machine (Gear 4+):** The most efficient gear at high speed, fitting for steady, predictable courses, but one must stay vigilant. Comfort can lead to inertia, and excessive speed without adaptability can lead to catastrophic failures.

The Agile Gearbox

The Gearbox's Assumptions: Everyone is a Driver, on Shared Roads

This gearbox assumes that every member of the organization is a driver, empowered to steer but synchronized to prevent collisions—illusions of shared understanding. It puts people in charge, but in unison, to avoid misunderstandings and misalignments. This approach emphasizes open communication — describing what one sees and experiences, enabling others also to choose the right gear and collectively navigate the organizational journey.

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The application of the agile gearbox metaphor is not limited to executive decisions. It is meant for meetings, teams, departments, and the entire organization, both at tactical and strategic levels. It encourages a systematic, repeated application that gradually evolves the organizational culture, ensuring the change is deep-rooted and sustainable.

By adopting this gearbox approach, organizations place individuals in the driver's seat—empowered, yes, but in concert with one another, avoiding the chaos of uncoordinated change. It's a step towards a culture where every voice navigates the journey, every hand can shift the gear, and every eye watches for the signs of change to ensure a smooth and successful journey toward true agility.

The Agile Gearbox: Translating Nature's Lessons into Mechanistic Terms

The agile gearbox metaphor serves as a mechanistic translation of natural metaphors, providing a tangible framework for understanding and implementing Organizational Agility (OA). Each aspect of this metaphor aligns with a principle from the natural metaphors discussed earlier, offering a practical approach to agile transformation.

The agile gearbox, introduced as a machine-like approach to organizational agility, encapsulates several natural metaphors within its framework. Each gearbox component aligns with a fundamental aspect of agile transformation, enhancing the understanding and implementation of agility in organizations.

Learning Safety (a): Cultivating a Safe Space for Transition (a)

Switching from automatic to manual in the context of organizational agility is akin to learning a new skill. It requires time, space, and a safe environment for practice. Just as a learner driver needs supervision and coaching, organizations need guidance and support during this transition. It is important to create a safe space for experimentation and learning, where mistakes are part of the learning process and not feared.

Nurturing Curiosity and Transparency (b): Developing Sensory Awareness

The gearbox metaphor extends to developing a heightened sense of awareness within the organization, similar to a nervous system. It's about cultivating curiosity and transparency, encouraging members to develop new "sensors" to detect both internal and external signals. This approach involves training everyone to pay better attention to the "noises" and "feelings" within the organization, enabling a more responsive and adaptive culture.

Emphasizing Care and Wellbeing (c): Maintenance as an Organizational Imperative

In vehicles, regular maintenance is essential for optimal performance. Similarly, in organizations, care and wellbeing are crucial. The gearbox metaphor underscores the need for ongoing "maintenance" of the workforce, ensuring their health, wellbeing, and professional growth. This aspect is vital for sustaining agility over the long term.

Building Trust through Reliable Transmission (d): Ensuring Smooth Coordination

In Organizational Agility, trust can be compared to a vehicle's transmission system, a critical component for ensuring smooth and coordinated operation. Just as a reliable transmission ensures seamless gear shifts in a car, trust within an organization facilitates smooth transitions and efficient cooperation among team members. This trust encompasses both affective (emotional) and cognitive (rational) elements, akin to how a clutch in a car allows for adaptable control between different states of motion. Cultivating Adaptive Relational Trust (ART of trust) is essential for an organization to function fluidly and respond effectively to changing circumstances.

Key strategies for building and maintaining this trust include:

- **Collaborative Decision-Making via the Advice Process:** As outlined by Frederic Laloux[Laloux14], this process emphasizes the importance of inclusivity and collective wisdom in decision-making. By actively seeking and valuing the input of all relevant stakeholders, organizations ensure that decisions are made not just swiftly, but with a comprehensive understanding of the various facets of each issue. This inclusive approach enhances trust, as individuals feel heard and valued, leading to decisions that are more robust and well-rounded.
- **Conflict Management through Nonviolent Communication (NVC):** Marshall B. Rosenberg's NVC[Rosenberg03] offers a powerful framework for addressing and resolving conflicts in a constructive and empathetic manner. By focusing on empathetic listening and expressing needs clearly without aggression, NVC fosters an environment where conflicts become opportunities for growth and understanding, rather than sources of persistent tension. Implementing NVC within an organization strengthens trust by demonstrating a commitment to respectful and effective communication, even in challenging situations.

Incorporating these approaches into the organizational fabric enhances trust and reinforces the agile framework, making the organization more resilient and adaptable in the face of change.

Fostering Equity Among All Parts (e): Recognizing the Importance of Every Component

In a vehicle, every part, whether visible or not, is essential for its overall functioning. This idea translates into the organizational context, where every member, regardless of their role, is vital. The gearbox metaphor encourages attention to all parts of the organization, especially those less visible, advocating for equity and inclusiveness. This approach can start with tangible actions like reducing hierarchies and creating more open and collaborative workspaces.

Intrinsic Motivation: The Self-Propelling Vehicle (f): Autonomy and Direction

Intrinsic motivation within the agile gearbox metaphor is compared to a self-propelling vehicle. It highlights that the organization, like a vehicle, should be autonomous, directing its path and propelled by the motivation and drive of its members. This aspect of the metaphor stresses that true agility comes from within, not imposed externally.

Leveraging Versatility for Adaptation (g): Embracing Diverse Contexts

Versatility is crucial in the journey towards Organizational Agility (OA), much like the varied gears of a car's gearbox adapting to different driving conditions. This concept reflects the ability to adapt tactically and strategically to evolving contexts. Echoing Henry Mintzberg's organizational forms, it suggests that organizations must be ready to switch between different organizational forms as circumstances dictate. This agility enables effective navigation through diverse and changing environments, emphasizing the need for contextual flexibility and readiness for adaptation.

Many sources of inspiration for this versatility employ the Open Space technology, a method for hosting large group discussions without a pre-planned agenda. Participants create and manage their own agenda of parallel working sessions around a central theme, leading to self-organized and spontaneous team formation. This approach aligns well with the concept of versatility, as teams formed through Open Space are more adaptable and can naturally adjust their organizational form to suit the context and goals. Below are five key models that exemplify this approach:

- **Fluid Meetings with Liberating Structures:** Liberating Structures [LipmanowiczMcCandless14] are a catalog of simple, inclusive microstructures that enhance engagement and collaboration in meetings. They enable facilitators to pick, choose, and combine different structures to suit specific contexts and goals, transforming traditional meetings into dynamic, interactive sessions for collective exploration and idea-sharing.
- **FaST Approach:** FaST (Fluid Scaling Technology [Quartel15]) offers a method and framework that emphasize rapid adaptation and flexibility in team structures. It advocates for responsive and dynamic team formation, allowing organizations to adjust quickly to new challenges and opportunities.
- **unFIX Model:** The unFIX model [Appelo22] includes an optional dynamic reteaming approach, providing organizations with the ability to fluidly change team compositions based on evolving project needs and goals.
- **Tesla/SpaceX's Daily Open Spaces:** Tesla and SpaceX's approach to creating dynamic teams through daily open spaces [Justice23] is a testament to the power of versatility in action. This method facilitates spontaneous collaboration and idea exchange, fostering an environment where innovation is not just encouraged but is a daily practice.
- **BOSSA nova Framework:** The BOSSA nova approach [EcksteinBuck20] combines Beyond Budgeting, Open Space, Sociocracy, and Agile to foster company-wide agility. This method emphasizes flexibility and responsiveness, aligning diverse methodologies for a holistic agile environment.

By integrating the principles of these models, organizations can develop a greater capacity for agility. Adopting versatile structures and practices ensures that teams are not only equipped to handle current challenges but are also prepared for future shifts in the business environment. This proactive approach to versatility allows organizations to stay ahead in a rapidly evolving world, making agility a core competency and strategic advantage.

Embracing Manual Driving in Organizational Agility

The journey toward true organizational agility is akin to learning to drive a manual car after being accustomed to automatic. This final subsection, leading into practical applications, emphasizes the shift from an autopilot mode of operation to a more conscious, adaptable, and manually controlled approach.

The core invitation of this section is to move away from routine, rote methods of working — what we term as “autopilot”. In autopilot mode, organizations often compromise their ability to adapt, losing agility in the process. This autopilot can also manifest as rigid, externally imposed structures and processes. True agility, however, requires embracing learning through playfulness (a), constant alertness and an openness to change directions if the journey demands it.

The metaphorical installation of a manual gearbox in an organization signifies the beginning of a new way of working. This process starts with minimal training for everyone, integrated into onboarding processes to ensure a foundational understanding of this new approach.

The transition to manual involves relearning or enhancing certain skills. It requires curiosity and the development of new senses, akin to a driver becoming attuned to the nuances of their unique vehicle.

In the domain of human neurobiology, exteroception involves the perception of external stimuli, while interoception is the internal sensing of physiological states. The recent research advancements by Critchley and Garfinkel [CritchleyGarfinkel17] highlight the nuanced influence of these perceptions on our emotions and decision-making capabilities. In the same way a skilled driver must be attuned to both the road ahead and the sensations of their vehicle, organizations must balance the external and internal awareness — their exteroception and interoception — to navigate effectively through their business landscape. Exteroception, akin to monitoring the road through a car’s windshield, mirrors, and external sounds, together with Interoception, similar to feeling the car’s performance through the steering wheel, pedals, and engine vibrations, give organizations a picture of their current context. By balancing both exteroception and interoception, organizations can more accurately ascertain if the current approach, or “gear,” is appropriate for the situation, ensuring a more holistic and responsive approach to agility.

Switching gears in this context is about practicing organizational fluency — the ability to seamlessly adapt to different situations, much like an experienced driver intuitively knows when to shift gears. This fluency is a skill that develops over time, through persistent practice and experience.

The shift from autopilot to manual driving in organizations is not an overnight transformation. It’s a journey that takes weeks of practice to become proficient and months to truly master. Organizations must be prepared for this journey, recognizing that becoming an experienced “mechanic” in this new way of working requires time, patience, and continuous learning.

As organizations progress along their journey from autopilot to manual driving, embracing the principles of the agile gearbox, they begin to recognize the intricacies and nuances of this transformative process. This evolution from a novice state to a level of expertise in agile practices is not just about mastering individual components of agility; it’s about integrating these elements (structure and culture) into a cohesive and comprehensive approach.

This is where “The ROAD: Reaching Organizational Agility Deliberately” comes into play.

4. The ROAD: Reaching Organizational Agility Deliberately

We need to control the development of software by making many small adjustments, not by making a few large adjustments, kind of like driving a car. This means that we will need the feedback to know when we are a little off, we will need many opportunities to make corrections, and we will have to be able to make those corrections at a reasonable cost. — Kent Beck

Crafting Your Agility Dashboard: Measuring the Aspects of a Superculture of Agility (SCA)

As organizations embark on the transformative journey towards Organizational Agility (OA), the first crucial step is establishing a reliable system for monitoring progress. This involves crafting an “Agility Dashboard” — a set of indicators and measures that provide real-time insights into the health and effectiveness of your agility initiatives. Think of it as the dashboard in a vehicle, constantly informing the driver about the vehicle’s status and needs. But in the context of agility, what exactly should your dashboard display? What should grab your attention as you navigate the path to agility?

Forget traditional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and metrics; the Agility Dashboard focuses on agility culture metrics. These metrics are derived from an exhaustive analysis of values in existing Agile methodologies (see Appendix 1) and the broader ecosystem (Appendix 2). The goal is to capture the essence of a Superculture of Agility (SCA), reflecting the core aspects that drive and sustain agility in an organization.

The following aspects provide an overview of the types of metrics and indicators that should be featured on your Agility Dashboard. These are designed to be assessed easily without requiring specialized tools, in keeping with the spirit of agility’s simplicity and directness (KISS - Keep It Simple, Stupid).

1. **Play and Growth Mindset (a):** Does your organization exhibit a collective growth mindset, as defined by Carol S. Dweck [Dweck06]? Are there signs of “Coachability” within teams and individuals?
2. **Transparency and Psychological Safety (b):**
 - Assess your organization’s culture of discovery and information flow according to the Westrum model [Westrum04]. How well do your teams and departments function as sensors, demonstrating curiosity and openness?
 - Evaluate collective psychological safety, potentially using frameworks like Amy C. Edmondson’s [Edmondson18] or Timothy Clark’s ‘Four Stages of Psychological Safety’ [Clark20].
3. **Care and Wellbeing (c):** Incorporate measures for wellbeing and self-care, referencing resources like NIOSH [NIOSH21] or Christine Porath’s work [Porath16].
4. **Team Trust (d):** For team-level trust, use models like those proposed by Costa and Anderson [CostaAnderson11]. At the organizational level, consider adopting OECD guidelines for measuring trust [OECD17].
5. **Equity (e):** Measuring equity in the workplace is a comprehensive endeavor, involving assessments of

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leadership accommodation for workers with disabilities, pay equity, incentive systems, and workforce diversity across various demographics.

6. **Intrinsic Motivation (f):** Utilize the Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (IMI) [IMI14] from Self-Determination Theory [DeciRyan85] to gauge the level of intrinsic motivation within teams.
7. **Versatility and Organizational Fluency (g):** Determine if individuals and teams can accurately assess their context and reorganize accordingly, demonstrating organizational fluency.

It's important to recognize that these measures are not static. The journey to agility is dynamic, and the metrics on your dashboard should evolve to integrate new concerns and insights. This ongoing adaptation ensures that your organization remains responsive and true to the principles of agility.

Regularly consulting and analyzing the data from your Agility Dashboard enables you to make informed decisions and adjustments, steering your organization towards a culture that embodies and breathes agility at every turn.

Transformation Cheat Sheet: Adopting a Superstructure of Agility (SSA)

Navigating the Shift to Contextual Organizing

The journey to Organizational Agility (OA) is not just about adopting new practices; it's a radical shift in how organizations operate and think. This part of the roadmap, our transformation cheat sheet, is a call to action to embrace a Superstructure of Agility (SSA). It's about experimenting with the agile gearbox, being attentive to the internal state of your organization, and fostering a culture of continuous learning and adaptation.

Steps to Install and Operate the Agile Gearbox

1. **Teach Organizational Fluency (g) & Learn the Forms:** The first step is to impart understanding and skills around organizational fluency (g). This involves teams and leaders learning (a) about different organizational forms (Personal Enterprise, Project Pioneer, Professional Assembly, Programmed Machine) and how to switch between them depending on the context.
2. **Use in Existing Meetings or Projects:** Begin applying the agile gearbox concepts in current meetings or projects. Encourage teams to experiment with different gears, assessing which is most appropriate for their current challenges and objectives.
3. **Create "Collectives" for Dynamic Organizing:** Inspired by models like FaST Agile [Quartel15], consider merging teams or creating collectives that can dynamically reorganize. This approach allows for flexibility and responsiveness to emerging needs and opportunities.
4. **Rotate Roles to Develop Empathy and Trust:** To build a deeper understanding and trust (d) among team members, rotate roles within the organization. This practice helps everyone appreciate different perspectives and challenges (b), fostering a more cohesive and empathetic work environment (c).
5. **Remove Hierarchies and Foster Inclusion (e):** Consider reducing or eliminating traditional hierarchical structures. Focus on developing a culture of inclusion and Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI). Such changes can lead to more equitable (e) and collaborative workspaces.

Expectations from the Agile Gearbox Implementation

The agile gearbox is not a quick-fix solution but a tool that requires practice and patience. Implementing it involves a gradual shift in organizational culture and structure:

1. **Frequently Assess SCA Aspects:** Regular assessments of the SCA culture aspects (a-g) are crucial. These should not be seen as one-off evaluations but as ongoing conversations and reflections. Tools like ad hoc surveys can be instrumental in these assessments, providing insights into how well the aspects of SCA are being integrated and lived within the organization.
2. **The Dynamic Nature of the Journey:** Embrace the idea that the measures and approaches will evolve to integrate new concerns and insights. The journey of agility is dynamic, and the strategies and tools used may need to adapt as the organization progresses along its path. Pay attention to feedback from all levels of the organization and be ready to make adjustments.
3. **Community and Collaboration:** Building a community of practice around agility within the organization can provide support, share knowledge, and encourage collaboration. This community should include people at all levels and functions, reflecting an agile organization's inclusive and diverse nature.

Conclusion: SCA + SSA = Agile Agility

Reaching OA is about the intricate and dynamic interplay between the Superculture of Agility (SCA) and the Superstructure of Agility (SSA). The convergence of these two aspects — SCA and SSA — creates a state of “agile agility”, a term that encapsulates an organization's ability to be agile not just in one context but in all of them, and in practice, culture, and structure.

The concept of “agile agility” is not a final destination but a continuous process of adaptation and growth. It recognizes that the landscape of business and organizational challenges is ever-evolving and that agility is a perpetual journey of learning, adapting, and evolving. In this journey, the agility dashboard, the agile gearbox, and the transformation cheat sheet serve as guides, helping organizations navigate the complexities of this transformative process.

The combination of SCA and SSA leads to a form of agility that is deeply embedded in the organization's DNA. It's a holistic approach that balances the structural and cultural elements of agility, ensuring that organizations are not just agile in name but in action and spirit. As we look towards the future, such a comprehensive approach to agility will be key to thriving in an increasingly complex and unpredictable world.

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Appendix 1 - Agile Methodologies' Values and Their Link to the Superculture of Agility

Agile Methodology	Core Values	Corresponding Organizational Agility Principles (Shorthand)
Scrum, Scrum@Scale	Commitment, Focus, Openness, Respect, Courage	Transparency (b), Curiosity (a)
XP (eXtreme Programming)	Communication, Simplicity, Feedback, Courage, Respect	Transparency (b), Curiosity (a)
Kanban	Agreement (d), Understanding, Respect, Leadership, Flow, Customer Focus, Transparency, Balance, Collaboration	Trust (d), Transparency (b), Adaptability (g)
Reinertsen/SAFe (Scaled Agile Framework)	Unlock the Intrinsic Motivation of Knowledge Workers, Decentralize Decision-Making	Intrinsic Motivation (f), Transparency (b), Trust (d)
LeSS (Large Scale Scrum)	Transparency, More with Less, Customer-Centricity, Continuous Improvement, Systems Thinking	Transparency (b), Curiosity (a), Adaptability (g)

References for Agile Methodologies

- **Scrum, Scrum@Scale**
 - Jeff Sutherland and Ken Schwaber, "The Scrum Guide." <https://www.scrumguides.org/scrum-guide.html>.
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- **XP (eXtreme Programming):**
 - Kent Beck, "Extreme Programming Explained: Embrace Change." Addison-Wesley, 2000.
- **Kanban:**
 - David J. Anderson, "Kanban: Successful Evolutionary Change for Your Technology Business." Blue Hole Press, 2010.
- **SAFe (Scaled Agile Framework):**
 - Dean Leffingwell, "SAFe 5.0 Distilled: Achieving Business Agility with the Scaled Agile Framework." Addison-Wesley, 2020.
- **LeSS (Large Scale Scrum):**
 - Craig Larman and Bas Vodde, "Large-Scale Scrum: More with LeSS." Addison-Wesley, 2016.

This appendix provides a concise comparison between the core values of various agile methodologies and the corresponding principles of Organizational Agility as discussed in the article. These connections illustrate how established agile practices align with broader concepts of an agility culture within organizations.

Appendix 2 - Larger Agile Ecosystem and Its Link to the Superculture of Agility

The Agile Ecosystem encompasses various concepts and principles from different disciplines that contribute significantly to understanding the elements discussed in the article, offering a richer and more holistic understanding of Organizational Agility.

Psychological Safety (Amy Edmondson, Timothy Clark) (b2)

- Amy Edmondson's concept of psychological safety, crucial for team dynamics and innovation, is closely linked to the transparency and openness required for agility (b). Her work emphasizes the importance of creating an environment where individuals feel safe to take risks and express themselves, fostering a culture of learning and adaptation.
 - Amy C. Edmondson, "The Fearless Organization: Creating Psychological Safety in the Workplace for Learning, Innovation, and Growth." Wiley, 2018.
- Timothy Clark's work complements Amy Edmondson's psychological safety concept by providing a framework for building an inclusive culture where all team members feel safe to contribute. His model is a vital component in fostering a culture of openness (b) and trust (d), which is crucial for agility.
 - Timothy R. Clark, "The 4 Stages of Psychological Safety: Defining the Path to Inclusion and Innovation." Berrett-Koehler Publishers, 2020.

"Drive: Autonomy, Mastery and Purpose" (Daniel Pink) (f)

Daniel Pink's work on motivation, particularly the aspects of autonomy, mastery, and purpose, aligns with the intrinsic motivation (f) aspect of the agile gearbox. His principles reinforce the need for self-direction and personal growth, which are essential for fostering a motivated and agile workforce. - Daniel H. Pink, "Drive: The Surprising Truth About What Motivates Us." Riverhead Books, 2009.

DevOps' Westrum Organizational Culture (b)

The Westrum culture model, often discussed in DevOps and Agile contexts, categorizes organizations based on information flow and response to failure. This model is integral to creating a culture of transparency and psychological safety (b), which is essential for agile organizations. - Ron Westrum, "A Typology of Organisational Cultures," Quality and Safety in Health Care, 2004.

Self Development/Growth Mindset (Linda Rising) (a)

Linda Rising, in her keynote speech "The Agile Mindset," emphasizes the importance of a growth mindset for continuous self-development and learning. This concept is pivotal to fostering a culture of play and learning (a), where individuals and teams are encouraged to embrace challenges and grow.

“Happiness” (Appelo, Crisp) (c)

- **Jurgen Appelo:** Appelo’s book “Managing for Happiness: Games, Tools, and Practices to Motivate Any Team” offers practical ideas and tools for increasing engagement, motivation, and happiness in the workplace. It’s a comprehensive guide for managers looking to create a more inspiring work environment. <https://management30.com/books/managing-for-happiness/>.
- **Crisp:** the Happiness Index at Crisp (a consulting company based in Stockholm, Sweden, co-founded by Henrik Kniberg, a well-known figure in the Agile world) is an innovative tool designed to measure and track happiness levels within teams and organizations. It reflects an approach to understanding employee well-being and its impact on productivity and agility. <https://dna.crisp.se/docs/happiness-index.html>.

Reinertsen Lean Product Development Flow 2- Inspired SAFe Principles (b)

Reinertsen’s work is highly regarded in the field of product development and has influenced numerous agile and lean practices, including those adopted in frameworks like SAFe. His insights into product development efficiency are crucial for understanding how to achieve agility and responsiveness in organizational processes.

- **Donald G. Reinertsen:** “The Principles of Product Development Flow: Second Generation Lean Product Development.” This book presents a comprehensive set of principles and practices for improving product development processes, focusing on lean methodologies and enhancing flow efficiency (with added transparency using better flow metrics).
 - Donald G. Reinertsen, “The Principles of Product Development Flow: Second Generation Lean Product Development.” Celeritas Publishing, 2009.

Trust (Lencioni, Semco Style) (d)

Patrick Lencioni’s work and the Semco Style of management highlight the role of trust in organizations. Trust (d) is a cornerstone for building strong teams and an agile culture, where transparency, empowerment, and mutual respect are prioritized. - Patrick Lencioni, “The Five Dysfunctions of a Team: A Leadership Fable.” Jossey-Bass, 2002. - Ricardo Semler, “Maverick: The Success Story Behind the World’s Most Unusual Workplace.” Warner Books, 1993.

Organizational Fluency (Mintzberg, McChrystal) (g)

Organizational Fluency, as discussed by Henry Mintzberg and General Stanley McChrystal, refers to the ability of an organization to adapt and reconfigure itself efficiently. Mintzberg provides a structural perspective, while McChrystal’s “Team of Teams” approach offers insights into how large organizations can operate with the agility of small teams. - Henry Mintzberg, “Understanding Organizations... Finally!” op. cit, 2023. is a completely revised edition of “Structure in Fives: Designing Effective Organizations.” Prentice Hall, 1983. - General Stanley McChrystal, “Team of Teams: New Rules of Engagement for a Complex World.” Portfolio, 2015.

Liberating Structures (g)

Liberating Structures are a set of facilitation techniques that enable organizations to organize meetings and activities that are adaptable to the context and goals. They provide practical methods for engaging teams and ensuring that every voice is heard, aligning with the principles of Organizational Fluency (g). - Henri Lipmanowicz and Keith McCandless, "The Surprising Power of Liberating Structures: Simple Rules to Unleash A Culture of Innovation." Liberating Structures Press, 2013.